

Influence of Restoring Force Absence and Passive Power Take-Off on WavePiston Performance

Eugenio M. Gelos, Pedro O. Fornaro, Colm J. Fitzgerald, and John V. Ringwood

Abstract—WavePiston is a novel wave energy converter (WEC) comprising multiple energy collectors coupled on a string, each equipped with a sail designed to harness surge excitation from incoming waves. The current configuration features two main distinctive design characteristics that significantly impact its hydrodynamic behavior and control: (i) the lack of hydrodynamic restoring capabilities, and (ii) a passive Power Take-Off (PTO) facilitating unidirectional power flow, preventing power transmission from the PTO to the energy collector. Despite the significant WavePiston technology milestones, and high technology readiness level achieved, there has been limited attention in the literature to implementing state-of-the-art control strategies for this device, particularly evaluating how its unique design features influence overall performance. Therefore, this preliminary study aims to evaluate how the WavePiston distinctive characteristics impact on the following performance metrics: (i) power capture across various sea states, (ii) operational spaces of sail stroke and (iii) PTO control force, along with (iv) energy production in a specific wave climate. The results are unfolded into two layers of detail, using a visual approach to provide an intuitive overview of how the absence of restoring capabilities and the passive nature of the WavePiston PTO affect the device performance metrics.

Index Terms—WavePiston, Performance Assessment, Spectral Control, Passive PTO, Wave energy

I. INTRODUCTION

WAVEPISTON is a novel wave energy converter (WEC) that consists of multiple energy collectors coupled together on a string [1], as depicted in Figure 1a-1b. Each collector includes a sail, designed to harness the surge excitation from incoming waves and a hydraulic power take-off (PTO). To date, WavePiston has achieved significant technological milestones, including the recent installation of 3rd generation device

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Eugenio M. Gelos is a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Ocean Energy Research (COER), National University of Ireland, Maynooth (e-mail: eugenio.gelos@mu.ie)

Pedro O. Fornaro is a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Ocean Energy Research (COER), National University of Ireland, Maynooth, and Instituto LEICI, Universidad Nacional de La Plata (UNLP) - CONICET, Argentina. (e-mail: pedro.fornaro@mu.ie)

Colm J. Fitzgerald is a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Ocean Energy Research (COER), National University of Ireland, Maynooth (e-mail: colm.fitzgerald@mu.ie)

John V. Ringwood is the Director of the Centre for Ocean Energy Research (COER), National University of Ireland, Maynooth (e-mail: john.ringwood@mu.ie)

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Fig. 1: (a) WavePiston device illustration, consisting of multiple energy collectors coupled on a string. (b) Detail of a single energy collector equipped with a sail and a hydraulic PTO design to harness surge excitation from incoming waves.

at the PLOCAN offshore facilities in Gran Canaria [2], where testing is being conducted to evaluate the overall performance of the device. Insights gained from this experimental testing will inform future design refinements for an upgraded full-scale device intended for potential deployment on the northern side of Gran Canaria, located at approximately 28.5° latitude and -15.5° longitude.

Interestingly, the baseline configuration of the WavePiston device features a variety of distinctive characteristics that have significant implications for both its hydrodynamic behavior and control. First, since the sails are constrained to move horizontally and are assumed rigid, no hydrodynamic restoring force acts on the WEC. This distinguishes WavePiston from conventional wave energy converters that function as resonators and possess inherent self-centering capabilities, such as point absorbers and oscillating wave surge converters. Second, in its current configuration, the PTO is passive, meaning it allows only unidirectional power flow, preventing power transmission from the PTO to the energy collector.

WavePiston efforts have primarily focused on technological development, achieving significant advancement on its technology readiness level (TRL) index [1]. In the light of this, several studies have leveraged its high TRL, using the WavePiston device as a case study, to develop and implement WEC-to-site pairing techniques, and to conduct analyses for specific applications, such as desalination plants, with a strong emphasis on evaluating various economic factors [3]–[12]. Moreover, some performance assessments of WavePiston device have been conducted, mainly through experimental testing on offshore platforms [2], or in wave tanks [13], [14]. Additionally, [15] presents a preliminary performance assessment, based on simula-

tion of the WavePiston device using simple modelling techniques and monochromatic wave scenarios.

Therefore, to the best of the authors' knowledge, little attention has been given to the value of state-of-the-art control strategies for the WavePiston device, specifically regarding how its unique design characteristics affect its overall performance. Addressing this gap could provide valuable insights that not only have the potential to inform future iterations of the WavePiston design but also enhance the understanding of how to effectively develop control strategies for this specific WEC and help overcome its associated challenges.

Acknowledging the existing gap in the literature, the main objective of this preliminary study is to evaluate how (a) the absence of restoring capabilities in the WavePiston current baseline configuration and (b) the inherent passivity of the PTO affect the following performance metrics of the WEC: (i) power capture across various sea states, operational spaces of (ii) the sails stroke and (iii) PTO control force, as well as (iv) energy production in a specific wave climate. The results are presented in two layers of detail, employing a visual approach to facilitate an intuitive and versatile overview of how the absence of restoring capabilities and the inherent passivity of the WavePiston PTO affect the performance metrics. Additionally, the implications of the presented results for potential design refinement pathways of the WavePiston device are briefly discussed.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. First, the overall methodology and specific considerations for evaluating the various performance metrics of the WavePiston are outlined in Section II. Subsequently, Section III presents the WavePiston modelling approach, along with the formulation of the optimal control problem (OCP). Afterward, the numerical case study, involving the wave climate of a potential deployment site, is introduced, followed by an insightful analysis of the performance metrics in Sections IV and V, respectively.

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to evaluate how the absence of restoring capabilities in the WavePiston current baseline configuration, and the inherent passivity of its PTO, affect the performance metrics, four different WEC configurations, itemized in Table I, are assessed considering the wave climate of a potential deployment site on the northern side of Gran Canaria. In Table I, $\textcircled{C1}$ corresponds to the WavePiston baseline configuration, which features no restoring capabilities and a passive PTO. The other WEC configurations add either a reactive PTO, capable of transmitting power to the energy collectors of the device, thus presenting a bidirectional power flow, or an external spring mechanism, to the energy collectors, providing them with a restoring force and self-centering capabilities.

The selected wave climate is represented by a limited number of sea states. For each of these sea states, the optimal controller is evaluated for the four proposed WavePiston configurations. It is essential to note that, to achieve realistic simulations and representative

TABLE I: Evaluated WavePiston configurations.

PTO TYPE	RESTORING CAPABILITIES	
	No Added Spring	External Spring
Passive	$\textcircled{C1}$	$\textcircled{C2}$
Reactive	$\textcircled{C3}$	$\textcircled{C4}$

performance assessment, the control formulation must adequately incorporate the physical constraints inherent to the WEC. Specifically, the WavePiston device is characterized by limitations on the allowable stroke and the maximum PTO control force. Furthermore, the constraint associated with the current passive PTO enforces unidirectional power flow that the control system must also accommodate effectively. Particularly, the challenges associated with correctly handling power constraints are greater than those related to position and control force limitations, and available literature on this subject is more limited [16].

Although several WEC control techniques are available in the literature [17]–[19], it should be noticed that not all can simultaneously manage position and control force constraints. Additionally, a significant number of control techniques rely on the transmission of reactive power from the PTO to the energy collector [20], [21]. However, these techniques cannot be applied to the WavePiston, at least for configurations $\textcircled{C1}$ and $\textcircled{C2}$, which feature a passive PTO. As a result, the overall options for control techniques that can simultaneously manage position, force, and power flow constraints are significantly reduced.

In this context, model predictive control (MPC) and MPC-like techniques are probably the most suitable for addressing the challenges associated with constraint handling in the WavePiston device [16]. Within this family of controllers, a spectral approach [22] is selected for this study, due to its ability to effectively address all relevant WavePiston constraints, while also providing a computationally efficient method for solving the associated OCP. This enhanced efficiency is particularly important for this study, given the various configurations that must be assessed across different sea states within the selected wave climate, resulting in a large number of simulation runs, as will be detailed in Section IV.

Finally, it is worth noting that, although the WavePiston baseline configuration includes multiple energy collectors coupled on a string, each equipped with a sail and PTO as depicted in Figure 1a, the analysis carried out in this study is focused on a single energy collector, for the sake of simplicity and to facilitate straightforward analysis and conclusion extraction. Next, the modelling approach for the WavePiston device is presented, along with the formulation of the associated OCP.

III. WAVEPISTON MODELLING AND OPTIMAL CONTROL PROBLEM FORMULATION

The hydrodynamics of the WavePiston device, featuring only one energy collector equipped with a single

sail, possessing one degree of freedom in the surge direction, can be described using Cummins' equation:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + \int_{-\infty}^t K(t-\tau)v(\tau)d\tau + S_h x(t) = F_{ex}(t) - F_u(t), \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ and $v(t)$ are the horizontal position and velocity of the sail, respectively, $M = m_w + m_\infty$ is the total mass, comprising the mass of the WEC (m_w) and the infinite added mass asymptote (m_∞) due to radiation effects. Additionally, S_h represents the restoring coefficient, $K(t)$ is the radiation kernel impulse response, $F_{ex}(t)$ is the wave excitation force, and $F_u(t)$ is the control force applied by the WavePiston PTO. Importantly, although the baseline (C1) configuration lacks restoring capabilities, the associated term is included in dynamic equation (1), since configurations (C2) and (C4) incorporate an external spring, resulting in a non-zero value of S_h .

Typically, the OCP associated with maximizing the useful energy conversion over a finite time horizon T_0 , subject to the WEC physical constraints, is defined as:

$$\max. : \quad \mathcal{J} = \int_0^{T_0} F_u(t)v(t)dt, \quad (2)$$

$$s.t. : \quad |x(t)| \leq x_{max}, \quad (3)$$

$$|F_u(t)| \leq F_{u|max}, \quad (4)$$

$$p_u(t) = F_u(t)v(t) \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\forall t \in [0, T_0],$$

where \mathcal{J} represents the energy absorbed by the WEC, $p_u(t)$ is the time-varying power of the PTO, while x_{max} and $F_{u|max}$ are the position and PTO control force physical constraints, respectively. Importantly, the power constraint stated in (5) is associated with the WavePiston inherent passive PTO, characterized by unidirectional power flow. However, since one of the objectives of this article is to evaluate how this power flow constraint affects the performance of the device, reactive PTOs will be assessed in configurations (C3) and (C4). In these cases, the power constraint (5) is removed, and the OCP is formulated as described in expressions (2)-(4). Further details on the OCP framework are provided next.

A. Optimal Control Problem Framework

In this study, a spectral approach is employed to solve the OCP defined in (2)-(5). This framework employs a truncated zero-mean Fourier series to approximate the OCP, following the methodology introduced in [22]. As a result, the approximations for the WavePiston velocity, excitation force, and control force are given by:

$$v(t) \approx \tilde{v}(t) = \Phi(t) \mathcal{V}, \quad (6)$$

$$F_{ex}(t) \approx \tilde{F}_{ex}(t) = \Phi(t) \mathcal{E}, \quad (7)$$

$$F_u(t) \approx \tilde{F}_u(t) = \Phi(t) \mathcal{U}, \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\square}$ notation indicates the discrete approximation of the continuous function, and $\Phi(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$ denotes the vector of basis functions defined as:

$$\Phi(t) = [\phi_1(t), \phi_2(t), \dots, \phi_{N/2}(t)]. \quad (9)$$

Here, the n -th component is represented as the following two-dimensional vector-valued function:

$$\phi_n(t) = [\cos(n\omega_0 t), \sin(n\omega_0 t)], \quad (10)$$

where ω_0 is the Fourier series fundamental frequency and n indicates a multiple of it. Similarly, \mathcal{V} , \mathcal{E} , and \mathcal{U} represent the vectors of coefficients associated with the corresponding Fourier truncated series, for the WEC velocity, excitation force, and control force, respectively, defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{V} = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{N/2}]^T, \quad \text{with } v_n = [v_{n1}, v_{n2}]^T, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{E} = [e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{N/2}]^T, \quad \text{with } e_n = [e_{n1}, e_{n2}]^T, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{U} = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{N/2}]^T, \quad \text{with } u_n = [u_{n1}, u_{n2}]^T. \quad (13)$$

Additionally, the time-derivative and primitive expression of any discretized function can be obtained introducing the time-derivative block diagonal matrix \mathcal{D} , defined as

$$\mathcal{D} = \bigoplus_{n=1}^{N/2} \mathcal{D}_n = \bigoplus_{n=1}^{N/2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & n\omega_0 \\ -n\omega_0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where \bigoplus denotes the direct sum operator. Considering this, the position and acceleration of the WEC are approximated as

$$x(t) \approx \tilde{x}(t) = \Phi(t) \mathcal{D}^{-1} \mathcal{V}, \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{v}(t) \approx \tilde{\dot{v}}(t) = \Phi(t) \mathcal{D} \mathcal{V}. \quad (16)$$

Furthermore, making use of the Galerkin method, consisting on writing the dynamic equations in residual form, and then minimizing the residual by imposing its orthogonality to all the elements of the basis [22], Cummins equation (1) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathcal{G}_w \mathcal{V} = \mathcal{E} - \mathcal{U}, \quad (17)$$

where \mathcal{G}_w is the WEC transfer matrix, defined by:

$$\mathcal{G}_w = \bigoplus_{n=1}^{N/2} \mathcal{G}_{w,n} = \bigoplus_{n=1}^{N/2} \begin{bmatrix} B_w(n\omega_0) & X_w(n\omega_0) \\ -X_w(n\omega_0) & B_w(n\omega_0) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

Here, $B_w(n\omega_0)$ and $X_w(n\omega_0)$ are the n -th elements of the WEC transfer matrix, defined as

$$B_w(n\omega_0) = B_r(n\omega_0), \quad (19)$$

$$X_w(n\omega_0) = n\omega_0 \left(m_w + m_r(n\omega_0) + m_\infty - \frac{S_h}{(n\omega_0)^2} \right). \quad (20)$$

Note, $B_r(\omega)$ represents the radiation damping and $A(\omega) = m_r(\omega) + m_\infty$ denotes the added mass due to radiation effects. These values are typically obtained using Boundary Element Method software such as NEMOH, Capytaine, or WAMIT [23]–[25].

Within this framework, the OCP defined in (2)-(5) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\max. : \quad \tilde{\mathcal{J}} = \frac{T_0}{2} \mathcal{U}^T \mathcal{G}_w^{-1} \mathcal{E} - \frac{T_0}{2} \mathcal{U}^T \mathcal{G}_w^{-1} \mathcal{U}, \quad (21)$$

$$s.t. : \quad \tilde{x}(t_m) = \Phi(t_m) \mathcal{D}^{-1} \mathcal{G}_w^{-1} (\mathcal{E} - \mathcal{U}) \leq \pm x_{max}, \quad (22)$$

$$\tilde{F}_u(t_m) = \Phi(t_m) \mathcal{U} \leq \pm F_{u|max}, \quad (23)$$

$$\tilde{p}_u(t_m) = \mathcal{U}^T \Phi^T(t_m) \Phi(t_m) \mathcal{G}_w^{-1} (\mathcal{E} - \mathcal{U}) \geq 0, \quad (24)$$

$$\forall t_m \in \mathcal{T} = \{t_1, \dots, t_M\} \subset [0, T_0].$$

Therefore, this optimization problem seeks to determine the control force vector of coefficients \mathbf{U} that maximizes objective function (21), subject to constraints (22)-(24), which are enforced at the discrete collocation points t_m in the set \mathcal{T} , included within the continuous time horizon $[0, T_0]$.

1) *Considerations for Numerical Implementation:* It is important to emphasize that the optimization problem associated with configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$, defined by (21)-(23) (excluding the power constraint) features a quadratic objective function and is subject to linear constraints with respect to \mathbf{U} , related to both the position and control force. Importantly, these optimization problems can be efficiently solved using state-of-the-art quadratic programming (QP) solvers [16], [22], [26].

However, the inclusion of power constraint (24) in the OCP associated with $\textcircled{C1}$ and $\textcircled{C2}$, introduces a nonlinear constraint, therefore QP solvers can no longer be used to address this problem. In fact, the inclusion of this constraint significantly increases the complexity and computational demands of the optimization problem [16], [26]. To reduce the computational burden, the analytical gradient and Hessian of the objective function, and nonlinear power constraint, can be incorporated into certain nonlinear programming (NLP) solvers (e.g. nonlinear optimization algorithms available in MATLAB and Gurobi platforms). The corresponding analytical expressions associated with the OCP described in (21)-(24) are provided next.

The gradient of objective function (21) with respect to the control force vector of coefficients, denoted as $\nabla \tilde{\mathcal{J}} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, is defined as follows:

$$\nabla \tilde{\mathcal{J}} = \frac{T_0}{2} \mathbf{g}_w^{-1} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \frac{T_0}{2} (\mathbf{g}_w^{-1} + \mathbf{g}_w^{-T}) \mathbf{U}, \quad (25)$$

In addition, the Hessian of the objective function, $H(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, is defined as:

$$H(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}) = -\frac{T_0}{2} (\mathbf{g}_w^{-1} + \mathbf{g}_w^{-T}). \quad (26)$$

Furthermore, the gradient of the control power with respect to \mathbf{U} evaluated at the collocation point t_m , denoted by $\nabla \tilde{p}_u(t_m) \in \mathbb{R}^N$, is defined as:

$$\nabla \tilde{p}_u(t_m) = \Phi^T(t_m) \Phi(t_m) \mathbf{g}_w^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{U}) - \mathbf{g}_w^{-T} \Phi^T(t_m) \Phi(t_m) \mathbf{U}. \quad (27)$$

Ultimately, the Hessian associated with the control power at collocation point t_m , represented as $H(\tilde{p}_u(t_m)) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, is given by:

$$H(\tilde{p}_u(t_m)) = -\Phi^T(t_m) \Phi(t_m) \mathbf{g}_w^{-1} - \mathbf{g}_w^{-T} \Phi^T(t_m) \Phi(t_m). \quad (28)$$

It is important to note that the power constraints specified in (24) are enforced at discrete collocation points, resulting in a total of M constraints of the form $p_u(t_m) \geq 0$. Thus, each of these constraints has a corresponding gradient and Hessian, as defined in (27) and (28), respectively.

IV. NUMERICAL CASE STUDY

The numerical case study, involving the four configurations summarized in Table I, is detailed below. First,

Fig. 2: WavePiston hydrodynamic frequency response. (a) Magnitude and phase of the excitation force. (b) Radiation damping and added mass. Two normalized Bretschneider wave spectra (dashed line) of $T_{pk} = \{6.5, 19\}$ s, representing the lower and upper bounds within the sea states evaluated in this study, are included, for comparison, with the WavePiston hydrodynamic response.

the baseline WavePiston configuration is described, followed by the wave climate at the evaluation site and the spectral OCP characterization. Lastly, the criteria for defining the external spring value integrated to $\textcircled{C2}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ WavePiston configurations is outlined.

WavePiston energy collector features a sail with a width of 8 m, height of 4 m, and depth of 0.25 m. This configuration is parametrized in the BEM software Capytaine [24], assuming an infinite water depth and a wave direction perpendicular to the sail, to obtain the corresponding hydrodynamic frequency response, as shown in Figure 2.

Additionally, the wave climate for a potential installation site on the northern side of Gran Canaria, located at approximately 28.5° latitude and -15.5° longitude, is used to evaluate the performance of the proposed WavePiston configurations. The wave climate is characterized using ERA5 reanalysis, based on six years of historical values [27]. The overall data is condensed into a total of twelve sea states, resulting in the following sets of peak periods $\mathcal{S}_{T_{pk}} = \{6.5, 10.5, 14.5, 19\}$ and significant wave heights $\mathcal{S}_{H_s} = \{1.25, 2.75, 4.25\}$.

Figure 3a presents the occurrence color plot distribution, together with the labels indicating the corresponding occurrence for each sea state, denoted as \mathcal{O}_{ij} , where i and j correspond to the peak period and significant wave height from the sets $\mathcal{S}_{T_{pk}}$ and \mathcal{S}_{H_s} , respectively (with labels arranged in ascending order). Furthermore, it should be clarified that a Bretschneider wave spectrum is assumed for the wave realizations associated with each sea state used to evaluate the various WavePiston configurations.

To discretize OCP (21)-(24) a frequency span of $\omega_s = 20$ rad/s is utilized, using a total of $N/2 = 300$ frequencies, resulting in a fundamental Fourier frequency $\omega_0 = \omega_s/N/2 = 0.67$ rad/s, and a simulation time horizon of $T_0 = 2\pi/\omega_0 = 94.25$ s. This discretiza-

Fig. 3: Wave climate at the potential deployment site located in northern Gran Canaria. (a) Sea state occurrence. (b) Relative exploitable energy.

tion scheme provides a sufficient approximation of the WavePiston hydrodynamics represented in Figure 2, also capturing the higher frequency components needed for modelling rapid control variations. Additionally, a total of $M = 601$ equally spaced collocation points are employed to enforce constraints, with the first element of the set \mathcal{T} defined as $t_1 = 0$ s. Moreover, regarding the physical constraints, an allowable stroke of $x_{max} = 2$ m is set along with a maximum PTO control force of $F_{u|max} = 1$ MN. Finally, to obtain statistically meaningful results, 20 realizations for each sea state of the considered wave climate were used to evaluate the four proposed configurations, obtaining for each case the corresponding OCP solution. Overall, this procedure yields a total of 960 simulation runs.

A. Determination of the External Spring Value

As previously introduced, (C2) and (C4) incorporate an external spring into the baseline WavePiston configuration to provide restoring capabilities (see Table I). Although defining the optimal value for this component implies a challenging control co-design problem, requiring iteratively evaluating different configurations within the specific wave climate seeking to maximize energy conversion, among other objectives and constraints, this is beyond the scope of this preliminary study. Instead, a simpler approach to define the value of the external spring is adopted, based on the exploitable energy within the wave climate. This method is sufficient for the purposes of this article, as it allows evaluation of the general impact of integrating a spring into the baseline configuration.

In this context, Figure 3b illustrates the relative exploitable energy distribution for the wave climate under consideration, calculated as

$$E_{r,exp,ij}\% = 100 \frac{E_{exp,ij}}{\sum_{ij} E_{exp,ij}},$$

where

$$E_{exp,ij} = \mathcal{O}_{ij} \rho g \int_0^{\infty} c_g(\omega) S_{\omega,ij}(\omega) d\omega$$

is the exploitable energy for the ij sea state; additionally ρ represents the water density, g is the acceleration due to gravity, c_g the group velocity, and $S_{\omega,ij}$ denotes the Bretschneider wave spectrum of the corresponding sea state. As can be seen in Figure 3b, the available energy within the wave climate is concentrated on the sea state with $(T_{pk}, H_s) = (14.5, 2.75)$. This observation constitutes the basis for defining the value of the external spring, designed so that the WavePiston

device resonates at the frequency associated with the peak period of the most energetic sea state, specifically $T_{pk} = 14.5$ s. This results in a choice of $S_h = 2.45 \times 10^4$ N/m.

V. RESULTS ANALYSIS

This section presents the results obtained by solving the OCP for the four WavePiston configurations listed in Table I, evaluated under the wave climate described in Section IV. An analysis of the results is conducted, focusing on how the absence of restoring capabilities and a passive PTO influences the following performance metrics: (i) power capture across the various sea states under analysis, (ii) sail stroke and (iii) PTO control force operational spaces, as well as (iv) energy production in the specified wave climate. To achieve this, the metrics corresponding to configurations (C2), (C3), and (C4) will be compared against the baseline configuration of the WavePiston device, denoted by (C1).

A. Power Capture Performance Metrics

This subsection evaluates the performance indices associated with the power capture of the WavePiston configurations (C1)–(C4) for the sea states defined by $\mathcal{S}_{T_{pk}}$ and \mathcal{S}_{H_s} , as described in Section IV. The left column of Figure 4 displays the normalized power capture distribution for the different configurations across the different sea state, calculated as

$$\bar{P}_{nor,ij}^{(k)} = \bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)} / \bar{P}_{max}^{(k)},$$

where $\bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)}$ denotes the mean power capture at the ij sea state, and $\bar{P}_{max}^{(k)}$ is the maximum mean power capture across all sea states, for the (Ck) WavePiston configuration. Each color plot also includes text labels that indicate the peak-to-mean power ratio, for each of the analyzed sea states.

Notably, configurations (C3) and (C4), which incorporate a reactive PTO, exhibit identical normalized power capture distribution, regardless of the presence of an external spring; thus, they are presented together in Figure 4c_i. However, the peak-to-mean power ratios for these two configurations differ, as indicated by the labels in the upper-left and lower-right corners for each sea state in Figure 4c_i, corresponding to (C3) and (C4), respectively. Further details regarding these differences are discussed in Section V-C, when analyzing the control force performance metrics.

Interestingly, regardless of the WavePiston configuration, the color plots in Figure 4 reveal that the power capture distribution across the various sea states exhibits a similar behavior: it increases for shorter peak periods and larger significant wave heights, with a notable concentration in the upper-left corner. The enhanced power absorption associated with shorter periods (on left hand-side of color plots) can be related to the hydrodynamic frequency response shown in Figure 2, where larger excitation force magnitudes are observed at higher frequencies, where the lowest peak period ($T_{pk} = 6.5$ s) wave spectrum is located. Note this scenario contrasts with heave point absorbers, which typically display the excitation force peak at a lower frequency range [28].

Fig. 4: Power capture performance metrics across different sea states for (a) $\textcircled{C1}$, (b) $\textcircled{C2}$, and (c) $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$. (a_i)-(b_i)-(c_i) Normalized power capture together with labels indicating the peak-to-mean power. (a_{ii}) Bar representation of $\textcircled{C1}$ normalized power capture. (b_{ii})-(c_{ii}) $\textcircled{C2}$ and $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$ power ratio with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$.

Furthermore, Figure 4a_{ii} displays a 3D bar chart of the normalized power capture for configuration $\textcircled{C1}$ ($\bar{P}_{nor,ij}^{(1)}$) across the various sea states, which is equivalent to the color representation on the left. This format allows for easier comparison with the power capture ratios between the different WavePiston configurations with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$ across the various sea states, defined as $\bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)}/\bar{P}_{ij}^{(1)}$, and concisely referred to as $(Ck/C1)$. In this way, Figure 4b_{ii} shows $C2/C1$ power capture ratios, and Figure 4c_{ii} jointly represents the power capture ratios $C3/C1$ and $C4/C1$. Thus, the middle and bottom right representations in Figure 4 illustrate the changes in normalized power capture for $\textcircled{C1}$ when an external spring and a reactive PTO are incorporated into the baseline configuration.

Moreover, Figures 4b_{ii} and 4c_{ii} show that, while all three variations of the baseline configurations present a power capture enhancement, especially for longer periods and lower wave heights, the incorporation of a reactive PTO in $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ leads to the most significant power capture increases. In particular, for $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ configurations, Figure 4c_{ii} reveals that the changes in power capture, show less sensitivity to variations in the peak periods of the sea states, compared to the differences observed with varying wave heights. Notably, the maximum increase in power capture for $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ configurations is up to 2.79 times that of the baseline configuration at the point $(T_{pk}, H_s) = (19, 1.25)$. However, caution is warranted when interpreting these results, as the highest increments in power capture for $C2/C1$ as well as for $C3/C1$ and $C4/C1$, correspond with the lowest normalized power capture values in

Fig. 5: Sail stroke performance metrics across different sea states for (a) $\textcircled{C1}$, (b) $\textcircled{C2}$, and (c) $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$. (a_i)-(b_i)-(c_i) RMS position together with labels indicating the peak values. (a_{ii}) Bar representation of $\textcircled{C1}$ RMS position. (b_{ii})-(c_{ii}) $\textcircled{C2}$ and $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$ RMS position ratio with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$.

$\textcircled{C1}$, as can be appreciated by comparing Figure 4a_{ii}, 4b_{ii}, and 4c_{ii}. This suggests that such increments may not represent substantial improvements in the overall WavePiston mean normalized power capture across all sea states, calculated as $1/12 \sum_{ij} \bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)}$, where k represents the configuration identification, and ij denotes the different sea states. In fact, the mean normalized power capture across all sea states shows only an 8% increase for configuration $\textcircled{C2}$ (which includes an external spring) compared to $\textcircled{C1}$, while configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$, including a reactive PTO, reveal a more significant increase of 35%.

B. Stroke Performance Metrics

This subsection evaluates changes in the stroke operational space associated with the WavePiston configurations $\textcircled{C1}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$. Figure 5 presents three color plots in the left column, showing the root-mean-square (RMS) positions of the sail, denoted as $x_{u,rms,ij}^{(k)}$, where k and ij indicate the WavePiston configuration and the corresponding sea state, respectively. The peak positions reached by $\textcircled{C1}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$ configurations within the evaluated wave climate, are also indicated by text labels, revealing that the WEC allowable stroke is reached in all cases. Notably, configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$, which incorporate a reactive PTO, exhibit identical RMS position metrics, regardless of the addition of an external spring. Consequently, they are plotted together in the lower row, Figure 5c, similar to the representation of power capture in Figure 4c.

Figures 5a_i and 5a_{ii}, associated with the baseline WavePiston configuration, show that the RMS position of the sail is more sensitive to variations in significant wave height than to changes in peak period, within

the evaluated wave climate. A similar trend can be observed for configuration $\textcircled{C2}$ in Figure 5b_i, and configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ in Figure 5c_i. Additionally, Figure 5b_i demonstrates that incorporating a spring into the baseline configuration increases the RMS position values at higher periods and wave heights.

Furthermore, the RMS position ratios across the different sea states for configurations $\textcircled{C2}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$, calculated as $x_{u|rms,ij}^{(k)}/x_{u|rms,ij}^{(1)}$ with $k=2,3,4$, are analyzed next. Figure 5b_{ii} illustrates the RMS position ratios $C2/C1$ for the various sea states; while Figure 5c_{ii} shows the RMS position ratios $C3/C1$ and $C4/C1$. It is evidenced that, when a spring is added to the baseline configuration in $\textcircled{C2}$, the increases in the RMS position are predominantly directed towards sea states with higher peak periods and lower wave heights, as shown in Figure 5b_{ii}. A similar trend is observed for configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$, which include a reactive PTO. However, Figure 5c_{ii} reveals that these configurations exhibit greater sensitivity to significant wave heights variations, displaying a subtle valley around $T_{pk} = 10.5$ s, with the RMS position ratio increasing towards both lower and upper peak period values. Moreover, a comparison of Figures 5b and 5c, corresponding to configurations $\textcircled{C2}$ and $\textcircled{C3}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$, indicates that incorporating a reactive PTO tends to further amplify motion, resulting in overall higher RMS position indices.

C. PTO Control Force Performance Metrics

In this subsection, the control force performance metrics for configurations $\textcircled{C1}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$ are analyzed. The RMS control force, denoted as $F_{u|rms,ij}^{(k)}$ where k represents the WavePiston configuration, and ij the corresponding sea state, is evaluated first. The color plots in the left column in Figure 6, reveal a consistent overall pattern across all configurations, with RMS control force values for the different sea states, increasing as the peak period shortens and the significant wave height rises, reflecting a gradient that points towards the upper-left corner of the plots. Additionally, unlike the position constraints shown in Figure 5, the physical constraints on the control force are not reached for all sea states or configurations. Specifically, the PTO force physical constraints are not met for the largest peak periods and lower wave height sea states. Nonetheless, the peak control force values across all configurations rise from the lower-right corner towards the upper-left corner, as represented in Figure 6, following the same increasing trend as the RMS force.

Furthermore, Figure 6b_{ii}, which displays the RMS control force ratios $C2/C1$ for each sea state, calculated as $F_{u|rms,ij}^{(2)}/F_{u|rms,ij}^{(1)}$ suggests that adding a spring to the baseline configuration of the WavePiston reduces the RMS control force in nearly all sea states. Interestingly, this effect is more pronounced around the 14.5 s peak period, where the inclusion of the spring is designed to achieve resonance of the WEC. Notably, this reduction in RMS control force occurs despite the increased power capture observed across all sea states in configuration $\textcircled{C2}$, as illustrated in Figure 4b_{ii}.

Fig. 6: PTO control force performance metrics across different sea states for (a) $\textcircled{C1}$, (b) $\textcircled{C2}$, (c) $\textcircled{C3}$, and (d) $\textcircled{C4}$. (a_i)-(b_i)-(c_i)-(d_i) RMS control force together with labels indicating the peak values. (a_{ii}) Bar representation of $\textcircled{C1}$ RMS control force. (b_{ii})-(c_{ii})-(d_{ii}) $\textcircled{C2}$, $\textcircled{C3}$, and $\textcircled{C4}$ RMS control force ratio with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$.

In addition, the RMS control force ratios $C3/C1$ and $C4/C1$ across the sea states, i.e., $F_{u|rms,ij}^{(k)}/F_{u|rms,ij}^{(1)}$ with $k=3,4$, shown in Figures 6c_{ii} and 6d_{ii}, respectively, also show a valley surrounding $T_{pk} = 14.5$ s. Moreover, a behavior similar to that observed for the RMS position ratios in Figure 5c_{ii} is evident in Figures 6c_{ii} and 6d_{ii}, in which the RMS force ratios $C3/C1$ and $C4/C1$ increase towards both lower and upper peak period values of the sea states.

Interestingly, while the inclusion of a reactive PTO in $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ results in the highest power capture, showing equal power in both cases as indicated in Figure 4, these configurations also show considerably lower RMS and peak control forces across the various sea states, compared to $\textcircled{C1}$, as observed in Figures 6c and 6d. Additionally, these two figures also show that, the configuration $\textcircled{C4}$, incorporating the external spring, achieves slightly lower RMS and peak control force values across all sea states, thus being the best configuration on the control force performance metrics.

D. Energy Production Performance Metrics

The final performance index analyzed for the WavePiston device is the relative energy production for each sea state, defined as

$$E_{r,ij}^{(k)} \% = 100 \mathcal{O}_{ij} \bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)} / E_T^{(k)},$$

Fig. 7: Energy production performance metrics across different sea states for (a) $\textcircled{C1}$, (b) $\textcircled{C2}$, and (c) $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$. (a_i)-(b_i)-(c_i) Relative energy production. (a_{ii})-(b_{ii})-(c_{ii}) $\textcircled{C1}$ relative energy production. (b_{ii})-(c_{ii}) $\textcircled{C2}$ and $\textcircled{C3\&C4}$ energy production percentage increments with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$ together with corresponding label indicating the overall increment of energy production.

where k denotes the WavePiston configuration, ij the sea state, and $E_T^{(k)} = \sum_{ij} O_{ij} \bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)}$ represents the total energy production of the corresponding configuration, for the given wave climate. Importantly, note the relative energy production is defined by weighting the mean power capture for each sea state, (\bar{P}_{ij}), by its corresponding occurrence (O_{ij}). As shown in the left column of Figure 7, the color plots for all WavePiston configurations indicate that the relative energy production is highly concentrated in sea states characterized by shorter periods and lower wave heights. Additionally, since configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ exhibit the same power capture distribution (see Figure 4), they produce the same energy output and are therefore plotted together in this context.

Note, the sea states associated with higher relative energy production for configurations $\textcircled{C1}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$, practically coincide with the most frequently occurring sea states, as evidenced by comparing the left column of Figure 7 with Figure 3a. Interestingly, the relatively low normalized power capture (Figure 4) observed in these more common sea states results in the highest relative energy production.

Furthermore, Figure 7a_{ii} presents a bar chart illustrating the relative energy production for configuration $\textcircled{C1}$ (equivalent to the one on its left). Subsequently, Figures 7b_{ii} and 7c_{ii}, depict the variations in relative energy production for configurations $\textcircled{C2}$ - $\textcircled{C4}$ per sea state, calculated as

$$\Delta E_{r,ij}^{(k)} \% = E_{r,ij}^{(1)} \% \left(O_{ij} \bar{P}_{ij}^{(k)} / O_{ij} \bar{P}_{ij}^{(1)} - 1 \right),$$

where k and ij denote the corresponding configuration

and sea state, respectively. Note in Figure 7b_{ii} for configuration $\textcircled{C2}$ (incorporating an external spring) that, although the maximum change in relative energy production occurs at the sea state defined by $(T_{pk}, H_s) = (10.5, 1.25)$, the most energetic sea state still remains in the lower-left corner, as depicted in Figure 7b_i.

Additionally, when incorporating a reactive PTO in configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$, Figure 7c_{ii} shows that the most significant change in relative energy production is observed in the sea state characterized by the shortest peak period and the lowest significant wave height. This results in an even greater concentration of energy production in the lower-left corner for these specific configurations, compared to $\textcircled{C1}$, as evidenced in Figure 7c_i.

Furthermore, the total variation, with respect to $\textcircled{C1}$, in relative energy production for configuration k , along the given wave climate, is calculated as follows:

$$100 \left(E_T^{(k)} - E_T^{(1)} \right) / E_T^{(1)} = \sum_{ij} \Delta E_{r,ij}^{(k)} \%.$$

Considering this, it can be appreciated in Figure 7b_{ii} that, adding a spring in configuration $\textcircled{C2}$ leads to an approximate 12% increase in total energy production. In contrast, the incorporation of a reactive PTO in configurations $\textcircled{C3}$ and $\textcircled{C4}$ has a much more substantial impact on the relative energy production, yielding a 65% increase, as indicated in Figure 7c_{ii}.

E. Technology Development Implications

The results presented in the previous subsections offer valuable insights that have the potential to inform future design refinements of WavePiston technology. While one of the primary objectives is to increase the device energy production, it is essential to consider additional metrics to contextualize potential design modifications. For instance, increased energy production may come at the expense of exaggerated WEC motion. Although a larger RMS position is not inherently problematic, having an operational stroke space too close to the end stops could represent a risk for the device integrity and may also increase the probability of failure. Moreover, a larger control force operational space may require more robust PTO components, potentially leading to increased costs. Another critical performance metric to consider is the peak-to-mean power ratio, especially since it can take large values, as illustrated in Figure 4. Note that a high peak-to-mean power ratio can result in over-dimensioning of the PTO and its associated components, thus making it important to keep this ratio as close to unity as possible.

Overall, it is essential to emphasize that any insights gained from the performance metrics intended to guide design strategies, must be considered alongside their technological implications, including economic factors, associated risks, failure probabilities, and all relevant aspects affecting the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of the device. Although such an analysis is beyond the scope of this article, the performance metrics and analyses of the four configurations presented in this

Performance Improvement	PASSIVE PTO		REACTIVE PTO	
	No Added	External	No Added	External
	Spring	Spring	Spring	Spring
	Ⓒ1	Ⓒ2	Ⓒ3	Ⓒ4
RMS Position	Green	Yellow	Red	Red
Peak Position	max	max	max	max
RMS Control Force	Red	Yellow	Green	Green
Peak Control Force	Red	Yellow	Green	Green
Power Capture	Red	Yellow (+8%)	Green	Green (+35%)
Power Ratio C_k/C_1	Red	Yellow	Green	Green
Peak-to-Mean Power	Red	Yellow	Green	Green
Energy Production	Red	Yellow (+11.9%)	Green	Green (+65%)

Fig. 8: Condensed representation of performance metrics results for each WavePiston configuration. The red-yellow-green color pattern provides an intuitive comparison of performance across the different configurations evaluated for each specific metric, with green indicating the best performance.

study provide a valuable starting point for evaluating various design pathways.

To facilitate navigation and comparison of the different performance metrics evaluated across the various WavePiston configurations within the selected wave climate, the most important results are summarized in Figure 8. This representation employs a simple color scheme to provide an intuitive performance comparison among the configurations for each specific metric, where the scale ranges from red to green, with green indicating the best performance (refer to the *Performance Improvement* scale in Figure 8). As a result, this color representation facilitates a quick overview of the implications of integrating a spring and/or a reactive PTO into the WavePiston baseline configuration, with further details available in Figures 3 through 7, along with their associated analyses if needed. Below, a summary of the key results that could influence design considerations is provided, leveraging the condensed information depicted by Figure 8.

1) *Main Implications of Integrating an External Spring on Performance Metrics:* To begin with, adding a spring to the baseline configuration, specifically in Ⓒ2 case, slightly increases the RMS position for all sea states while reducing the RMS control force for nearly every sea state, as shown in the two-color representation in Figure 8, with minimal impact on the peak control force values. Although there is improvement in the mean power capture for each sea state, the greatest increases occur in the sea states where the device exhibits lower overall power capture, as discussed in Section V-A. This results in an overall improvement of 11.9% in total energy production, with respect to Ⓒ1, for the given wave climate. Nonetheless, as suggested by the color pattern in Figure 8, the addition of a spring yields performance metrics better than Ⓒ1, but it is surpassed by the addition of a reactive PTO in all metrics except for the RMS position.

2) *Main Implications of Integrating a Reactive PTO on Performance Metrics:* When integrating a reactive PTO into the WavePiston device in configurations Ⓒ3 and Ⓒ4, instead of the passive PTO used in Ⓒ1, the motion of the device tends to be exaggerated, resulting in a

higher RMS position for all sea states. Consequently, this leads to a lower performance metric, as indicated by the red color pattern in Figure 8. However, as discussed in Section V-C, both the RMS and peak control forces across all sea states, are significantly reduced compared to Ⓒ1, making it the preferable option for these metrics. Among the two configurations using a reactive PTO, Ⓒ4, which also incorporates an external spring, demonstrates the best control force indices, achieving the lowest RMS and peak values for all sea states within the analyzed wave climate, as indicated by the brighter green pattern in Figure 8.

Furthermore, both configurations Ⓒ3 and Ⓒ4 exhibit the greatest increase in power capture per sea state, along with reduced peak-to-mean power ratios, making them superior options for this power performance indices. Although both configurations have the same mean power capture, Ⓒ4 shows a slight improvement in the peak-to-mean power ratio across the different sea states. Finally, the relative energy production for Ⓒ3 and Ⓒ4 is the same across all sea states, representing the highest values among the evaluated configurations, shown in green in Figure 8. Notably, this represents a 64% improvement on the total energy production compared to Ⓒ1.

3) Considerations for the Interpretation of the Results:

While this preliminary study provides a comprehensive overview of performance metrics across various WavePiston configurations in relevant sea states and effectively addresses challenges posed by nonlinear power constraints, certain assumptions should be considered when interpreting the results.

The integration of reactive PTO achieves the maximum power capture within the various sea states analyzed across all configurations; however, this comes with the trade-off of the highest peak-to-mean power ratio, usually associated with higher losses [16]. It is worth noting that, in this study the PTO has been modeled as ideal, neglecting dynamics and losses within the electrical system. This simplification could be particularly relevant for reactive PTO, as the energy loss associated with delivering power from the PTO to the WEC may be comparable to, or even exceed, the energy gained through the control strategy [29]. Additionally, this work employs a linear hydrodynamic model omitting nonlinear effects, such as viscous drag, which can also have an impact on the design of energy maximizing controllers. Incorporating more detailed hydrodynamic effects and PTO efficiency considerations could influence control strategy outcome and the total power output, thus caution should be exercised when directly extrapolating the results presented here.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates the impact of the lack of restoring capabilities and the inherent passivity of the WavePiston PTO on the device performance. To achieve this, three variations of the baseline configuration Ⓒ1 are proposed, featuring either an external spring and/or a reactive PTO. A case study is presented in which the OCP is solved for each sea state in

the wave climate of a potential deployment site using a spectral control approach. Importantly, this work provides insights on how to reduce the computational burden of solving the OCP using this framework. The results facilitate the evaluation of performance metrics related to (i) power capture across various sea states, (ii) operational spaces of the sail stroke and (iii) PTO control force, as well as (iv) energy production in a particular wave climate.

The resulting performance metrics are presented in two layers of detail, providing a quick visual overview of the various performance indices for each of the configurations, while allowing for deeper evaluation and analysis when needed. Overall, the addition of a reactive PTO in configurations (C3) and (C4) demonstrates the most significant improvement in energy production compared to the baseline configuration (C1). It also significantly reduces the peak-to-mean power ratio, which could be relevant for avoiding the overdimensioning of the WEC components. Additionally, the operational space for the control force has been significantly reduced by using a reactive PTO, potentially allowing for less robust components and consequently lowering overall costs.

However, the benefits obtained by incorporating the reactive PTO, come at the cost of increasing the stroke operational space of the sail, moving the RMS position values for different sea states closer to the allowable stroke of the WavePiston device. Among the two configurations integrating a reactive PTO, (C4), which also integrates an external spring, slightly outperforms (C3) in all the evaluated performance metrics. On the other hand, while adding only an external spring to the baseline configuration, namely configuration (C2), also improves the performance metrics, the benefits are considerably less significant compared to those obtained by including a reactive PTO.

Finally, while this preliminary study focuses on the performance metrics of the WavePiston device without delving into the techno-economic aspects resulting from actually integrating an external spring or a reactive PTO, it establishes a solid foundation for future research exploring these economic considerations, where the minimization of LCOE is often regarded as the ultimate goal. Additionally, it highlights the significance of addressing the design of the external spring using a control co-design approach. These two areas suggest potential directions for future research stemming from this study.

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